

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable 4.6

Report on Mission dashboard concept and findings for tracking of Mission progress

Planned delivery date: 31/03/2025

Actual submission date: 27/05/2025

Report leader: FHG

Authors: Laura Vetter (FHG)

Type of deliverable: Report

Work package Leader: WP4 - ERINN

Version: 2.0

Project founded by the European Commission within the HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01	
Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
PP Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO Confidential, only for member of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

Start date of the project: June 1st, 2022

www.Prepare4Blue.eu

Funded by the European Union, through its Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101056957 (PREP4BLUE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the granting authority, the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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“PREP4BLUE: Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters” has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Program call “*Preparation for deployment of ‘lighthouse demonstrators’ and solution scale ups and cross-cutting citizen and stakeholder involvement (HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-01)*”, Grant Agreement n° 101056957.

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VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Authors (Institution)	Notes
0.1	04.03.2025	Laura Vetter (FHG)	First version.
1.0	31.03.2025	Patrick Bethke (FHG)	Finalised version. Review changes only.
1.1	31.03.2025	Patrick Bethke (FHG)	Final partner review
1.2	10.04.2025	Patrick Bethke (FHG)	Revisions for submission after WP-level feedback
1.3	24.04.2025	Laura Vetter (FHG)	Final version after feedback
1.4	30.04.2025	Anna-Line Cantrel (Ifremer)	Coordination review
1.5	06.05.2025	Eirini Apazoglou (EuroMarine)	Coordination review
1.6	22.05.2025	Laura Vetter (FHG)	Revision after coordination feedback
1.7	23.05.2025	Cécile Nys (Ifremer)	Final review by coordination & Layout update
1.8	26.05.2025	Laura Vetter (FHG)	Addressed final comments
2.0	27.05.2025	Laura Vetter (FHG)	Final version to submit

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
AC	Acceptance Criteria
DB	Database
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
(the) Mission	Mission Ocean and Waters
MO	Mission Ocean and Waters
MOE	Mission Ocean Ecosystem
P4B	PREP4BLUE
RE	Requirements Engineering
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

Executive Summary

Missions are a new instrument in the Horizon Europe programme, which aims to tackle societal challenges with systemic solutions. The implementation of five Missions themes (Restore our ocean and waters by 2030, Adaptation to Climate Change, Cancer, Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and Soil Health and Food) was launched in 2021.

Funded under the EU Horizon Europe programme, Prep4Blue is a three-year project that sets the scene for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the objectives of the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (hereafter “MO” or (the) Mission) by using the dedicated enablers: the “Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System” and the “Public mobilization and engagement”.

Within PREP4BLUE (P4B), WP4 (*“Knowledge Management: Identifying and Transferring Knowledge/Solutions to Support the Mission”*) aims to support effective knowledge management, especially in helping to identify high potential knowledge/solutions and effectively transfer them to target end-users for uptake/application in support of the Mission.

Within the P4B project, *Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung EV (FHG)* is leading Task 4.5, which considers the work carried in T4.1-T4.4 to provide recommendations on how to build a dashboard and map to be used by the all the end-users of the Mission as well to allow to track the Mission progress. The WaveLinks platform, developed by SDU’s team in T4.2, is used as a basis for these recommendations. This platform has successfully implemented the Mission Ocean Ecosystem (MOE) ontology, as detailed in D4.1 and D4.3 to interlink projects, results and stakeholders. The recommendations provided in D4.6 aims to further develop WaveLinks after the end of P4B to become the *Mission Dashboard* that will meet all end-users needs as well as track the progress towards the Mission objectives and targets.

This document provides recommendations for the future implementation of the Mission dashboard and map, ensuring the integration of relevant projects, data, and key performance indicators (KPIs) for a comprehensive analysis of Mission progress.

1 Introduction

The Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 is a key initiative under Horizon Europe, aiming to drive transformative change through research, innovation, and stakeholder engagement. To effectively support this Mission, structured tools and methodologies are needed to facilitate decision-making and track progress. This report brings together two essential components: the Mission Dashboard concept and how it could support the tracking of Mission progress, both of which play a critical role in ensuring transparency, data-driven insights, and strategic alignment with Mission objectives.

The envisioned Mission Dashboard builds on top of SDU’s WaveLinks system, which already provides functionality for searching and evaluating projects and project outcomes related to the Mission Ocean and Waters, partially via SDU’s involvement in BlueMissionAA¹ and BlueMissionBANOS². This document focuses on how it can be improved to be useful for all stakeholders involved in the Mission as well as citizens.

In this document, Chapter 2 “Mission Dashboard Concept” introduces how the Mission Dashboard should be designed and developed building upon the progress made on the WaveLinks platform³. The Mission Dashboard aims to become a tool to facilitate data-driven decision-making by integrating relevant information, user needs, and visualization methods. This chapter explains the structured *Requirements Engineering (RE) process*⁴ used to define functionalities, acceptance criteria, and user-driven features. Figure 1 illustrates the RE workflow, detailing how user requirements translate into a fleshed-out dashboard concept that supports data integration and stakeholder engagement.

Figure 1. Dashboard Concept Development Workflow

Chapter 3 “Tracking of Mission Progress” focuses on the framework for monitoring and assessing Mission-related activities and outcomes. It explores the integration of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) within the dashboard and methods for measuring progress. Our study proposes recommendations for refining the methodology to improve long-term monitoring across European marine regions. There are strong methodological links to D4.5 (Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module).

By combining dashboard development and progress tracking, this report provides a comprehensive approach to supporting the Mission’s implementation and WaveLinks future development, ensuring that data and insights contribute effectively to the Mission objectives.

¹ BlueMissionAA bluemissionaa.eu

² BlueMissionBANOS bluemissionbanos.eu

³ WaveLinks wavelinks.eu

⁴ Klaus Pohl (2025). Requirements Engineering: Fundamentals, Principles, and Techniques. 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-662-69204-2.

2 Mission dashboard concept

This chapter introduces the Mission dashboard concept, explaining its purpose, structure, and role in supporting the Mission semantic network. A dashboard concept defines how data, insights, and key performance indicators (KPIs) are visually structured and made accessible to enhance situational awareness and inform decision-making. To develop a robust and effective dashboard, we apply *Requirements Engineering (RE)*, a systematic approach to identifying, analysing, and documenting the needs and constraints of stakeholders. RE helps translate often vague user demands into precise technical specifications that guide development. It acts as a bridge between what users want and what developers build. RE consists of key activities such as requirement elicitation, specification, validation, and management, ensuring that the Mission dashboard meets the functional and technical expectations of its users. By leveraging RE, we establish a well-defined conceptual foundation that enhances usability, interoperability, and relevance, supporting the implementation and monitoring of the Mission in Lighthouse areas.

2.1 User Stories and Acceptance Criteria

To ensure user-centred Requirements Engineering (RE), we use User Stories, a key method for capturing and structuring user needs, along with Acceptance Criteria to define success conditions. The current users of WaveLinks have been considered in the development of these user stories, ensuring their expectations are reflected in the RE process.

User stories help teams understand the expectations of end users, ensuring that development remains focused on real-world needs. They facilitate clear communication among team members, making requirements more transparent and actionable. By using user stories, we can prioritize development efforts effectively, keeping the Mission dashboard aligned with stakeholder needs. Additionally, they provide a foundation for defining test cases, such as Acceptance Testing and Usability Testing, to verify that features meet user requirements and function as intended.

User stories are brief, simple descriptions of a feature from the perspective of the end user. They are typically written in the format:

"As a [user], I want [feature] so that [benefit]."

[user]	Role/Persona/Stakeholder
[feature]	Goal/Need (The user's desired outcome or objective.)
[benefit]	Benefit/Reason: (Clarification of the importance of the feature in the context of the user's goals and the broader mission.)

Acceptance Criteria (AC) define the specific conditions that must be met for a feature, user story, or requirement to be considered complete and acceptable. They establish a clear, shared understanding among stakeholders, developers, and testers on what needs to be delivered. By outlining measurable and testable conditions, acceptance criteria help ensure alignment between user needs and technical implementation. They define the scope and boundaries of a feature, provide a basis for testing and validation, and reduce ambiguity and misinterpretation.

This structured approach ensures that user needs drive development, making the dashboard both functional and user-friendly.

The following user stories and ACs are structured according to stakeholder clusters. The clusters represent key stakeholder groups within the innovation ecosystem, each contributing to the success of the Mission. Their roles and functions are essential in bridging research and market-ready innovations.

The user stories and ACs presented in this study are the consolidated results of qualitative research carried out in close collaboration with participants of the P4B project and individuals connected to the project consortium from various stakeholder groups, as well as users of WaveLinks. Together, we explored needs, gathered feedback, and developed the use cases. The discussions were conducted with Prep4Blue partners in parallel with the development of WaveLinks, resulting in some of the requested functionalities already being implemented, as noted in the list below. This collection therefore provides empirical support for existing features and proposes useful future functionalities, particularly for the WaveLinks search interfaces for Funding, and for Policy & Legislation, which are yet to be implemented.

2.1.1 Academic and Research Institutions

Researcher – Case Study 1

*As a **researcher**, I want to explore past and ongoing research projects and their solutions and knowledge output, so that I can build on existing findings and avoid redundant work, identify gaps in research that need further investigation, assess the real-world impact of different research projects, and align my work with proven methodologies and best practices.*

- AC1: The Dashboard must provide a search function for research projects, with filters for project status (past, ongoing), research field, and keywords.
- AC2: Each research project entry should display key details, including objectives, findings, solutions, and knowledge output.
- AC3: The database should allow users to filter projects based on their relevance to specific ocean sustainability challenges.
- AC4: The system should provide links to relevant publications, methodologies, and impact assessments associated with each project.
- AC5: There should be an option to view related projects and knowledge gaps identified in previous research efforts.

Information on AC1-AC4 is already possible to obtain by using WaveLinks. Further improvements to WaveLinks will enable the achievement of AC5, ensuring users have access to all relevant information.

Researcher – Case Study 2

*As a **researcher**, I want to access a comprehensive database of research papers in my field, so that I can stay updated with the latest developments for informed decision-making, identify potential collaborators working on similar topics, generate new ideas that contribute to Mission Ocean's goals of ocean preservation and sustainability, and build on existing solutions to avoid duplication and enhance innovation.*

- AC1: The system provides a list of relevant papers sorted by publication date.
- AC2: Papers can be filtered by specific topics related to Mission Ocean (e.g., marine conservation, sustainable fishing).
- AC3: Users receive notifications about new publications in their field.
- AC4: The system offers summaries and key insights from each paper.

This user story will provide further improvements of WaveLinks, ensuring improved accessibility to research papers and collaboration opportunities.

Researcher – Case Study 3

*As a **researcher**, I want to learn about citizen engagement methods used in marine research, so that I can design outreach initiatives that effectively involve the public, increase data collection through participatory science approaches, ensure my research is accessible and relevant to society, and enhance public trust in marine science through transparent engagement.*

- AC1: The Dashboard must provide a dedicated section on citizen engagement methodologies, with real-world examples from marine research projects.
- AC2: Each method should include best practices, case studies, and effectiveness evaluations.
- AC3: Users should be able to filter engagement methods by research field, level of participation, and geographic region.
- AC4: The system should provide contact details or links to researchers and organizations using these methods for collaboration opportunities.

Users can already access all the information outlined in the ACs above through WaveLinks.

Researcher – Case Study 4

*As a **researcher**, I want to understand the transfer path from research to real-world applications, so that I can ensure my findings contribute to tangible solutions, identify industry and policy stakeholders interested in my work, secure funding for applied research and implementation, track how similar research has been successfully translated into practice, and maximize the societal and environmental impact of my research.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should provide a clear step-by-step overview of technology transfer processes, including commercialization and policy uptake.
- AC2: Users should be able to explore past case studies of successful research-to-application transitions.
- AC3: A stakeholder mapping tool should be available to help researchers identify relevant industry, government, and NGO partners.
- AC4: The system should provide information on funding sources specifically aimed at applied research and commercialization.
- AC5: Researchers should be able to track the progression of similar projects and view impact assessments.

In this case, WaveLinks provides information on AC3 and AC4. Further improvements to WaveLinks will allow to achieve AC1, AC2 and AC5, ensuring users have comprehensive access to all necessary information.

Researcher – Case Study 5

*As a **researcher**, I want to find information on funding opportunities for marine research projects, so that I can secure financial support to advance my research, align my proposals with current funding priorities and calls, collaborate with institutions that have successfully secured similar funding, and increase the chances of my project being implemented in real-world applications.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should provide a regularly updated database of funding opportunities, categorized by funding type, region, and research focus.
- AC2: Users should be able to set alerts for new funding calls relevant to their research field.
- AC3: Each funding opportunity entry should include details on eligibility, deadlines, and successful past applications.
- AC4: Researchers should be able to access a repository of successful grant proposals or summaries for reference.
- AC5: The system should provide networking options to connect researchers with institutions or consortia seeking partners for joint proposals.

Users can already access all the information described in the ACs above in WaveLinks.

Researcher – Case Study 6

*As a **researcher**, I want to explore policy briefs and reports related to my field, so that I can understand how my research connects to policymaking and societal impact, tailor my findings to be more relevant for decision-makers, contribute to evidence-based policies that drive ocean conservation efforts, identify research gaps that align with policy needs, and effectively communicate scientific insights to non-expert audiences.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should include a searchable library of policy briefs and reports categorized by topic, region, and policy relevance.
- AC2: Each document should be summarized with key insights and policy implications.
- AC3: Users should be able to filter documents by their relation to Mission Ocean goals and UN Sustainable Development Goals.
- AC4: A dedicated section should provide guidelines on translating scientific findings into policy recommendations.
- AC5: The system should allow users to track how policies have evolved in response to research findings.

This user story will provide further improvements to WaveLinks, ensuring enhanced accessibility to policy briefs and reports for more effective research integration into policymaking.

University administrator or academic program coordinator – Case Study

*As a **university administrator or academic program coordinator**, I want to access insights on marine research trends and skill demands, so that I can design curricula that align with current scientific and industry needs, foster interdisciplinary collaboration between departments and external research initiatives, better support students in pursuing careers in ocean-related fields, and identify opportunities for joint research projects and funding applications.*

- AC1: The Dashboard must provide an analytics dashboard displaying emerging research trends and skill demands in marine science.
- AC2: Users should be able to filter data by industry needs, policy priorities, and technological advancements.
- AC3: The system should include case studies of universities successfully aligning curricula with research trends.
- AC4: A networking feature should enable collaboration between institutions for joint research and funding applications.
- AC5: The Dashboard should provide insights into student career pathways and job market demand.

This user story will contribute to further developments in WaveLinks, providing university administrators with refined insights into marine research trends and skill demands to better align academic program with industry needs.

R&D centre director or project manager – Case Study

*As an **R&D centre director or project manager**, I want to explore available knowledge outputs and technology readiness levels (TRLs), so that I can identify research with high potential for commercialization, connect with universities, companies, and policymakers to accelerate innovation uptake, secure partnerships for pilot projects and testing new marine technologies, avoid duplication of effort and focus on complementary developments, and align our research strategy with real-world challenges and funding priorities.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should provide a searchable database of research outputs, categorized by technology readiness level (TRL).
- AC2: Each entry should include commercialization potential, funding history, and previous testing phases.
- AC3: Users should be able to filter technologies based on application sector, funding status, and pilot project availability.
- AC4: A collaboration tool should facilitate networking between researchers, industry, and policymakers.
- AC5: The system should provide insights on market trends and gaps for aligning research with real-world needs.

This user story will guide further enhancements in WaveLinks, facilitating access to knowledge outputs and technology readiness levels (TRLs) for improved commercialization and innovation uptake.

2.1.2 Business and Industry

Startup & Entrepreneur – Case Study

*As a **startup and entrepreneur**, I want to access information on available support opportunities in the blue economy, so that I can understand the market better and get ideas for innovation, learn about mentoring and funding opportunities and how to access them, collaborate with companies and technology providers interested in testing my solution, and showcase my product to gain visibility.*

- AC1: The Dashboard must provide a categorized list of support opportunities, including funding, mentorship, and partnerships.
- AC2: Users should be able to filter opportunities based on funding type, region, or industry focus.
- AC3: Each support opportunity must include details on eligibility criteria, application deadlines, and key contacts.
- AC4: A "connect" function should allow users to reach out to relevant organizations.

This user story will contribute to further improvements in WaveLinks, ensuring startups and entrepreneurs have enhanced access to relevant support opportunities in the blue economy.

Incubator & Accelerator – Case Study

*As an **incubator and accelerator**, I want to access information on innovative endeavours in the blue economy, so that I can offer my programs to promising startups and entrepreneurs, find potential candidates for incubation and support them in accessing the market, promote my program and success stories, and discover best practices from other programs in the sector.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should list startups and entrepreneurs working on marine innovations, with relevant project descriptions.
- AC2: Incubators must be able to contact potential candidates through a built-in messaging or connection feature.
- AC3: A section should showcase successful startups that have gone through incubation programs.
- AC4: A database of best practices for incubators and accelerators in the blue economy should be accessible.

This user story will guide future developments in WaveLinks, providing incubators and accelerators with structured insights into marine innovations and best practices for fostering successful entrepreneurship.

2.1.3 Legal and Intellectual Property

Intellectual Property Expert - Case Study

As an **Intellectual Property Expert**, I want to access a database of marine innovation patents and licensing agreements, so that I can assess existing patents and avoid potential infringements, identify opportunities for technology transfer and commercialization, advise researchers and startups on the best IP protection strategies, and support open-access initiatives while ensuring legal compliance.

- AC1: The system should provide a searchable database of patents and licensing agreements related to marine innovations.
- AC2: Users must be able to filter patents by industry sector, application type, and status (e.g., pending, granted, expired).
- AC3: The database should summarize of each patent, including ownership and licensing options.
- AC4: Users should have access to resources explaining different IP strategies (e.g., open source vs. commercial licensing).

This user story will contribute to further improvements in WaveLinks, enhancing accessibility to marine innovation patents and licensing agreements for intellectual property experts.

Legal Advisor – Case Study

As a **Legal Advisor**, I want to access an overview of international and national regulations on marine data sharing and open science, so that I can provide informed guidance on data licensing and intellectual property rights, help organizations comply with GDPR and other data protection laws, facilitate collaborations between public and private entities by clarifying legal frameworks, and compare regulatory differences across countries to support international projects.

- AC1: The Dashboard should offer a structured overview of relevant international and national marine data-sharing laws.
- AC2: Users should be able to compare legal frameworks by country or region.
- AC3: A section should summarize GDPR compliance for marine research and data use.
- AC4: Resources or case studies on public-private data-sharing agreements should be available.

This user story will support future developments in WaveLinks, providing legal advisors with structured insights into international and national regulations on marine data sharing and open science.

Researcher – Case Study 7

As a **researcher** developing marine technologies, I want guidance on copyright, patents, and open-source licensing options, so that I can choose the best IP strategy for protecting and sharing my work, avoid unintentional violations of existing patents or copyrights, and attract potential investors by demonstrating a clear IP roadmap.

- AC1: The Dashboard should provide an interactive guide comparing copyright, patent, and open-source licensing strategies.

AC2: A searchable repository of case studies on IP protection for marine technology should be available.

AC3: Users should be able to access legal templates for patent applications and licensing agreements.

This user story will guide enhancements in WaveLinks, ensuring researchers developing marine technologies have comprehensive guidance on copyright, patents, and open-source licensing options.

2.1.4 Financial and Investment

Investor & Venture capitalist – Case Study

*As an **investor and venture capitalist**, I want to access information on promising investment opportunities, so that I can diversify my investment portfolio and look for remunerative opportunities in the blue economy, assess the potential of startups and SMEs, benchmark my portfolio, and be matchmade with good companies to invest in.*

AC1: The Dashboard should provide a searchable database of startups and SMEs working on marine innovations.

AC2: Each startup/SME profile must include key investment details (e.g., funding stage, revenue model, traction).

AC3: Investors should be able to see aggregated insights on past and current investments in the blue economy.

AC4: A matchmaking feature should recommend potential investment opportunities based on investor preferences.

This user story will contribute to further improvements in WaveLinks, ensuring investors and venture capitalists gain enhanced access to promising investment opportunities within the blue economy.

2.1.5 Government and Regulatory

National Authority & Government Agency – Case Study

*As a **National Authority and Government Agency**, I want to access information on national, regional, and local initiatives to promote the blue economy, so that I can get ideas on how to foster a sustainable blue economy in my country, identify good practices, and learn about successful public-private partnership models.*

AC1: The Dashboard should provide an interactive repository of national, regional, and local blue economy initiatives.

AC2: Users should be able to filter initiatives by country, policy type, funding mechanism, and impact areas.

AC3: A section should highlight successful public-private partnerships with case studies.

AC4: Smart specialisation strategies should be accessible, with examples from various regions and sectors.

AC5: A dedicated section should map how different national policies align with Mission Ocean objectives.

This user story will support future developments in WaveLinks, providing national authorities and government agencies with structured insights into effective blue economy initiatives and public-private partnership models.

Regional Authority & Government Agency – Case Study

*As a **Regional Authority and Government Agency**, I want to access information on national, regional, and local initiatives to promote the blue economy, so that I can learn about smart specialization strategies, regional funding and collaboration schemes, and successful water and ocean management practices*

AC1: The Dashboard should provide a collection of regional smart specialisation strategies related to the blue economy.

AC2: Users must be able to access case studies on regional funding and collaboration models.

AC3: A searchable section should highlight interregional and transregional funding opportunities.

AC4: A knowledge base should showcase best practices in water and ocean management.

AC5: Users should be able to connect with relevant projects that align with their regional priorities.

This user story will guide improvements in WaveLinks, enabling regional authorities and government agencies to access relevant smart specialization strategies, funding schemes, and best practices in ocean management.

Regulatory Body – Case Study

*As a **Regulatory Body**, I want to access information on policies that favour or hinder the objectives of Mission Ocean, so that I can understand policy gaps and their implications for the development of the blue economy, identify good policies, and interact with stakeholders to understand what policies they need.*

AC1: The Dashboard should provide an analysis of policies that support or create barriers to blue economy growth.

AC2: A comparative tool should allow users to view policy landscapes across different regions and governance levels.

AC3: Users should be able to access expert commentary and case studies from stakeholders working in the field.

AC4: An interactive forum or consultation feature should enable regulatory bodies to engage with practitioners.

This user story will enhance WaveLinks by offering regulatory bodies comprehensive insights into policies that support or hinder the development of the blue economy, facilitating informed decision-making.

2.1.6 Support and Advocacy

Ocean Literacy Coordinator – Case Study 1

*As the **coordinator of an ocean literacy network**, I want to be able to search for past and current ocean literacy initiatives from around the world, so that I can replicate good practice examples in my country, track the evolution of ocean literacy initiatives, identify funding opportunities, support policymakers with evidence-based recommendations, and stay informed about emerging trends.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should provide a searchable database of ocean literacy initiatives, including key details such as location, goals, and outcomes.
- AC2: The system should allow users to filter initiatives by region, theme, and impact to track the evolution and adapt strategies.
- AC3: Users should access funding opportunities and collaboration partners for ocean literacy.
- AC4: The Dashboard should include policy recommendations and reports to support policymakers with evidence-based strategies.
- AC5: Users should be able to receive notifications about emerging trends and innovative approaches in ocean literacy.

This user story will support further improvements to WaveLinks, ensuring enhanced access to past and current ocean literacy initiatives for global knowledge exchange and strategic replication.

Ocean Literacy Coordinator – Case Study 2

*As the **coordinator of an ocean literacy network**, I want to be able to search for other ocean literacy networks from around the world, so that I can network, share best practices, explore potential partnerships, and coordinate efforts to amplify the impact of ocean literacy initiatives.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should allow users to search for and connect with other ocean literacy networks globally.
- AC2: Users should be able to find contact information, activities, and collaboration opportunities of other networks.
- AC3: A dedicated section for sharing best practices and success stories between networks should be available.
- AC4: The Dashboard should include tools for creating and promoting joint initiatives and funding opportunities.

This user story will contribute to the development of WaveLinks, enabling ocean literacy networks to connect, collaborate, and amplify their impact through shared best practices and joint initiatives.

Marine Conservation group Coordinator – Case Study 1

*As the **coordinator of a marine conservation group**, I want to be able to search a database of relevant policies from around the world, so that I can see good and bad examples, make informed decisions, identify policy gaps, and adapt proven strategies to my local context.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should provide a searchable database of global marine conservation policies, including details on marine protected area designation, enforcement, and effectiveness.
- AC2: Users should be able to filter policies by region, success rate, and policy type.
- AC3: The system should offer insights into policy gaps and opportunities to enhance marine conservation efforts.
- AC4: The Dashboard should provide examples of policies that can be adapted to specific regional contexts.

This user story will guide refinements in WaveLinks, providing marine conservation coordinators with structured insights into global policies, allowing for adaptation and strategic decision-making.

Marine Conservation group Coordinator – Case Study 2

*As the **coordinator of a marine conservation group**, I want to be able to search the database for other similar groups, so that I can build a network, engage with policymakers, collaborate on international efforts, exchange knowledge, and amplify advocacy efforts.*

- AC1: The Dashboard should allow users to search for and identify similar marine conservation groups based on themes, goals, and regions.
- AC2: Users should be able to access contact details, group activities, and partnership opportunities for collaboration.
- AC3: The Dashboard should provide features to facilitate engagement with policymakers and organizations that have implemented successful conservation policies.
- AC4: A resource section should be available for sharing knowledge, best practices, and success stories globally.

This user story will enhance WaveLinks, facilitating network-building among marine conservation groups and strengthening international collaboration, advocacy, and policy engagement.

2.1.7 Consumers and End Users

Person interested in participating in Citizen Science Initiatives – Case Study 1

As someone interested in taking part in citizen science initiatives, I want to be able to access the citizen science database of WaveLinks without having to register and enter a username and password, so that I can easily engage with the website, quickly find relevant initiatives, explore opportunities before committing, and share initiatives with others without requiring sign-up.

- AC1: Users should be able to access the WaveLinks citizen science database without mandatory registration.
- AC2: The database should provide search and filtering functionalities without requiring a login.
- AC3: Each initiative should have a shareable link that can be accessed by others without registration.
- AC4: Users should be able to browse initiative details without limitations.

Information on AC1-AC4 is already accessible via WaveLinks by registering. Further improvements should allow to access this information without prior registration, ensuring a more seamless user experience.

Person interested in participating in Citizen Science Initiatives – Case Study 2

As someone interested in taking part in citizen science initiatives, I want to be able to filter the citizen science database by EU Member State that the listed initiatives are active in, so that I can find local initiatives, contribute to scientific research in my region, and participate in initiatives that align with my interests and expertise.

- AC1: The database should allow users to filter initiatives based on EU Member States.
- AC2: The filter should display only initiatives that are active in the selected country.
- AC3: Users should be able to combine location filtering with other search criteria (e.g., topic, participation level).

Information on AC1-AC2 is already possible to obtain by using WaveLinks. Further improvements to WaveLinks will allow to achieve AC3 providing the users all the information they want.

Citizen Science initiative Organizer – Case Study 1

As the organizer of a citizen science initiative, within each entry on the WaveLinks citizen science database, I want to be able to click on the level of participation description (e.g., 'distributed intelligence') to bring up a description of what that means and what the other options are, so that I can design my initiative to be as inclusive and participatory as possible, understand where my initiative falls on the participation scale, compare different levels, and communicate the level of participation clearly to volunteers.

- AC1: Each participation level (e.g., "distributed intelligence") should be clickable and lead to a description of that category.
- AC2: The description should provide an overview of all participation levels in citizen science.
- AC3: Users should be able to compare different levels of participation side by side.

AC4: The Dashboard should provide guidance on selecting an appropriate level of participation based on initiative goals.

This user story will contribute to further improvements in WaveLinks, enhancing accessibility to participation-level descriptions to support more inclusive and participatory citizen science initiatives.

Citizen Science initiative Organizer – Case Study 2

*As the **organizer of a citizen science initiative**, I want to be able to access best practice information for setting up citizen science initiatives, so that I can attract and retain volunteers, align with Mission Ocean targets, design an inclusive and accessible initiative, and secure funding and institutional support.*

AC1: The Dashboard should include a resource section with best practice guides for citizen science initiatives.

AC2: Best practices should cover volunteer engagement, accessibility, funding, and institutional alignment.

AC3: Users should be able to filter best practices by relevant topics (e.g., funding, inclusivity).

Information on AC1 and AC3 is already possible to obtain by using WaveLinks. Further improvements to WaveLinks will allow to achieve AC2 providing the users all the information they want.

Ocean Literacy Partitioner – Case Study 1

*As an **ocean literacy practitioner**, I want to search for past and current ocean literacy initiatives, so that I can stay informed about best practices, connect with collaborators, discover new ideas, and identify successful approaches to adapt*

AC1: The Dashboard should provide a searchable database of ocean literacy initiatives.

AC2: Users should be able to filter initiatives by region, target audience, and key themes.

AC3: Each initiative entry should include details on methodology, impact, and potential collaboration opportunities.

This user story will support further developments in WaveLinks, enabling ocean literacy practitioners to efficiently search and filter past and current initiatives for enhanced collaboration and adaptation of successful strategies.

Ocean Literacy Partitioner – Case Study 2

*As an **ocean literacy practitioner**, I want to be able to filter projects based on the relevant seven ocean literacy principles and/or 10 ocean literacy dimensions, so that I can collate relevant work, focus on a subarea, identify gaps, and explore opportunities for new projects.*

AC1: Users should be able to filter ocean literacy projects based on the 7 ocean literacy principles and 10 ocean literacy dimensions.

AC2: The system should allow multiple filters to be applied simultaneously.

AC3: Users should be able to view filtered results in an easily accessible format, highlighting relevant projects.

This user story will contribute to further improvements in WaveLinks, ensuring ocean literacy practitioners can efficiently filter projects based on the seven ocean literacy principles and ten ocean literacy dimensions.

End User – Case Study 1

*As an **end user**, I want the display to be optimized for smaller screens (14 inches or smaller), so that I can use my device without layout issues like overlapping logos and menus and can access all website functions clearly.*

AC1: The page layout should dynamically adjust to different screen sizes (responsive design).

AC2: The menu should remain accessible without overlapping other UI elements.

AC3: Logos at the bottom should resize and reposition to prevent clutter.

This user story will enhance WaveLinks by optimizing the display for smaller screens, ensuring all website functions remain fully accessible without layout issues.

End User – Case Study 2

*As an **end user**, I want the filter boxes to automatically close when I click on another one, so that I can see the screen clearly without overcrowding and easily manage my selected filters.*

AC1: When a user selects a new filter box, any previously opened filter box automatically collapses.

This user story will support future refinements in WaveLinks, improving filter box functionality to prevent overcrowding and enhance user experience.

End User – Case Study 3

*As an **end user**, I want the "Solutions" tab to explain what "solutions" refers to, so that I can understand whether these are solutions to Mission Ocean-related problems or results from Mission-funded projects.*

AC1: A clear description is provided in the "Solutions" tab, explaining:

- Whether the solutions are related to Mission Ocean objectives.
- Whether the solutions are the results or deliverables from Mission-funded projects.

This user story will strengthen WaveLinks by providing clear explanations within the "Solutions" tab, clarifying the relevance of solutions in the context of Mission Ocean.

Non-expert Citizen User – Case Study

*As a **non-expert citizen user**, I want the filter for Mission Ocean objectives to display more descriptive text than just "1, 2, 3," so that I can understand the meaning of each objective and find relevant information more easily.*

AC1: The filter for Mission Ocean objectives displays descriptive text (e.g., "1: Protect and restore marine ecosystems") instead of just numbers.

AC2: A link to basic information on Mission Ocean is provided for further understanding.

This user story will improve WaveLinks by ensuring non-expert users can easily understand Mission Ocean objectives through descriptive text instead of numerical labels.

End User – Case Study 4

As an **end user**, I want a brief description to appear when I click on any tab under "Explore" (e.g., "projects", "stakeholders", "engagement methods"), so that I can better understand what I'm looking at, where the information came from, and how to use it effectively.

AC1: A dialog box or pop-up description appears when the user clicks on a tab under "Explore" (e.g., "projects", "stakeholders", "engagement methods").

AC2: The description provides the following:

- What the information represents.
- Where it comes from (e.g., data sources, Mission Ocean-related projects).
- How the user can utilize the information.

This user story will refine WaveLinks by offering informative descriptions within the "Explore" tab, helping users navigate and interpret the provided content effectively.

End User – Case Study 5

As an **end user**, I want a brief description of Mission Ocean with a link to the official page on the home screen, so that I can quickly understand the context of the website and get more information if needed.

AC1: A brief Mission Ocean description appears on the home screen with a link to an official page for users who need more details.

AC2: The description helps users understand the purpose and context of WaveLinks in relation to Mission Ocean.

This user story will enhance WaveLinks by incorporating a brief description of Mission Ocean on the home screen, with a direct link to official resources for further exploration.

2.2 Functionalities and Dashboard Requirements

This section outlines the functionalities and requirements that WaveLinks should enhance to become the Mission Dashboard. These functionalities are derived from the user stories and acceptance criteria described in the previous section. Functionalities define the specific features and actions the dashboard must support to meet user needs, while dashboard requirements establish the technical and design constraints necessary for implementation. By ensuring alignment with user expectations, this section provides a structured foundation for developing a dashboard that is both practical and user centric. In effect, this section outlines a vision for a future, complete WaveLinks iteration. Therefore, some functionalities are already present in WaveLinks.

2.2.1 Data and Information

This category encompasses the core content to underpin the Dashboard, offering valuable resources such as research databases, case studies, policy documents, and best practices. The data sources are largely modelled after SDU’s MOE database. It serves as a comprehensive hub for stakeholders to access key information on funding opportunities, ocean literacy, marine conservation, and innovation. With a focus on data accessibility, this section enables users to explore relevant policies, initiatives, and solutions—supporting informed decision-making and fostering a deeper understanding of ocean-related challenges and opportunities.

Table 2. Functionalities and Dashboard Requirements: Data and Information

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Projects, Research and Knowledge	
Display Research Project Details	Display key details for each research project, including objectives, findings, solutions, and knowledge output
Related Projects and Knowledge Gaps	Option to view related projects and knowledge gaps identified in previous research efforts
Summaries and Key Insights for Research Papers	Summaries and key insights for each research paper, highlighting main findings, methodology, and relevance.
Research Paper Database	List of relevant papers sorted by publication date
Case Studies of Curriculum Alignment	Case studies of universities successfully aligning curricula with research trends
Research Trends and Skill Demands Analytics	Dashboard visualizing emerging trends, skills in demand, and gaps in marine science education and research.
Stakeholders and Innovation	
Stakeholder Mapping Tool	Tool for mapping stakeholders (industry, government, NGOs) relevant to the user’s research
Searchable Database of Startups and SMEs	List of startups and SMEs working on marine innovations.
Startup/SME Profiles with Investment Details	Detailed profiles including key investment details (funding stage, revenue model, market traction and investor interest level).
Aggregated Insights on Investments in the Blue Economy	Dashboard showing investment trends in marine innovation, including funding volumes, active investors, and emerging markets.
Interactive Repository of Blue Economy Initiatives	List of national, regional, and local initiatives categorized by sector, impact, and funding sources.
Expert Commentary and Stakeholder Case Studies	Insights from professionals and real-world case studies on stakeholder engagement, policy impact, and business success.
Best Practices for Incubators & Accelerators	Database of best practices for incubators and accelerators in the blue economy
Student Career Pathways and Job Market Insights	Insights into student career pathways and job market demand highlighting skill demands, job trends, and opportunities for students.

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Funding and Support	
Searchable Section for Interregional Funding Opportunities	List highlighting available funding at interregional and transregional levels.
Funding Opportunity Details	Detailed view of funding opportunities, including eligibility criteria, deadlines, available funding amounts and past applications.
Display Categorized Support Opportunities	Organized list of support opportunities, including funding, mentorship programs, networking initiatives and partnership options.
Show Support Opportunity Details	Expanded view of each support opportunity, showing eligibility requirements, application process, key contacts, and deadlines.
Repository of Successful Grant Proposals	Collection of successful grant proposals or proposal summaries, providing insights into winning application strategies and formats.
Public-Private Data-Sharing Case Studies	Case studies and best practices on successful public-private data-sharing agreements, showcasing frameworks and impact.
Showcase Successful Public-Private Partnerships	Case studies of effective collaborations, illustrating best practices, funding structures, and outcomes.
Case Studies on Regional Funding and Collaboration Models	Examples of effective regional funding initiatives and collaboration models, showing how different stakeholders have leveraged funding and partnerships for success.
Policy and Legislation	
Searchable Library of Policy Documents	Library of policy briefs, reports, and legislative documents, categorized by topic, region, and policy relevance.
Searchable Database of Marine Conservation Policies	Database of global marine conservation policies, including details on marine protected area designation, enforcement mechanisms, and effectiveness.
Searchable Database of Marine Conservation Groups	Directory of marine conservation organizations based on themes, goals, and geographic focus, with contact and collaboration options.
Policy Document Summaries and Policy Implications	Summarized policy documents with key insights, relevance, and potential impact
Provide GDPR Compliance Summary	Summary of GDPR compliance requirements for marine research, data collection, and data-sharing activities.
Overview of Marine Data-Sharing Laws	Structured overview of international and national regulations on marine data sharing, with practical guidance on compliance and interoperability.
Access to Smart Specialisation Strategies	Collection of S3 from various regions and sectors, demonstrating best practices in blue economy development.
Collection of Regional Smart Specialisation Strategies	Repository of S3 tailored to regional economic and environmental priorities.
Insights into Policy Gaps and Opportunities	Tool highlighting policy gaps and opportunities for improving marine conservation efforts.
Examples of Adaptable Marine Conservation Policies	Examples of successful marine conservation policies that can be adapted to different regional contexts, with key success factors.
Guidelines for Translating Science into Policy	Section with guidelines and case studies for translating scientific findings into policy recommendations
Policy Recommendations and Reports for Ocean Literacy	Section for policymakers, featuring evidence-based strategies, policy recommendations, and reports on ocean literacy initiatives.

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Citizen Science and Ocean Literacy	
Citizen Engagement Methodologies	Section on citizen engagement methodologies including case studies, best practices, and evaluation metrics.
Best Practice Guides for Citizen Science Initiatives	Resources offering guidance on volunteer engagement, securing funding, ensuring inclusivity, and maximizing impact in citizen science projects.
Searchable Database of Ocean Literacy Initiatives	Database allowing users to explore past and ongoing ocean literacy initiatives worldwide
Display Key Details of Ocean Literacy Initiatives	Overview of each initiative, including location, objectives, key activities, and achieved outcomes.
Searchable Database of Ocean Literacy Networks	Directory of global ocean literacy networks, helping users identify and connect with relevant organizations and experts.
Show Methodology, Impact, and Collaboration Info for Ocean Literacy Projects	Detailed insights into how initiatives operate, their methodologies, measured impact, and potential collaboration opportunities.
Solutions and Best Practices	
Summarize Patents & Licensing Options	Overview of patents, ownership structures, and available licensing agreements.
Publications, Methodologies, and Impact Assessments	Links to relevant publications, methodologies, and impact assessments associated with each project and solutions.
Case Studies of Research-to-Application	Collection of case studies of successful transitions from research to real-world applications.
Searchable Marine Innovation Patents & Licensing Agreements	Database of patents and licensing agreements related to marine innovations.
Provide Legal Templates for Patents & Licensing	Repository of templates for patent applications and licensing agreements.
Technology Transfer Overview	Step-by-step overview of technology transfer processes, including commercialization pathways and policy uptake.
Case Studies on IP Protection for Marine Tech	Case study collection highlighting best practices for intellectual property (IP) protection for marine technology
Provide IP Strategy Resources	Guidance on different IP strategies (open source vs. commercial licensing)
Knowledge Base on Best Practices in Water and Ocean Management	Repository of best practices in sustainable water and ocean management, including policy recommendations.

2.2.2 Linkages

Linkages focus on defining how different data points or entities are connected across the Dashboard. This includes linking policies to case studies, initiatives to funding opportunities, and collaborators for citizen engagement. It helps users understand the relationships between various elements, such as comparing legal frameworks, tracking policy evolution, and exploring connections within the broader policy landscape. These functionalities facilitate smoother navigation and provide insights into how different components interact within the context of marine innovation and sustainability efforts.

Table 3. Functionalities and Dashboard Requirements: Linkages

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Track Progress of Similar Projects	Interactive dashboard to monitor project progression, including key milestones, impact assessments, and status updates.
Interactive Guide on Copyright, Patents & Licensing	Step-by-step comparison tool for intellectual property (IP) strategies, allowing users to explore copyright, patents, and open-source licensing models.
Mapping of National Policies and Mission Ocean Objectives	Visualization mapping national policies against Mission Ocean objectives, highlighting synergies and gaps.
Comparative Tool for Policy Landscapes	Side-by-side comparison tool enabling users to analyse policies across regions and governance levels, with filtering options.
Analysis of Policies Supporting or Hindering the Blue Economy	Dashboard feature categorizing policies into enablers and barriers for blue economy growth, with case studies.
Track Policy Evolution	Policy timeline tracker showing how regulations have changed over time in response to research, technological advancements, and socio-economic shifts.
Track Blue Economy initiatives	Interactive feature tracking initiative development, showing key updates, funding changes, and measurable outcomes.
Compare Legal Frameworks by Country	Searchable and filterable tool to compare marine data-sharing legal frameworks across multiple countries and jurisdictions.
Links to Collaborators for Citizen Engagement	Searchable directory of researchers, organizations, and projects using citizen engagement methodologies, with a "connect" feature for potential collaborations.

2.2.3 Search & Filter

This category focuses on providing users with efficient tools to find relevant information on the Dashboard. It offers powerful filtering options, allowing users to narrow down results based on criteria such as region, theme, policy type, or other key attributes. Whether searching for research projects, funding opportunities, or ocean literacy initiatives, the search and filter functionalities help users quickly access the most pertinent data, making navigation seamless and tailored to specific needs.

Table 4. Functionalities and Dashboard Requirements: Search & Filter

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Research Projects & Papers, Opportunities, Patents & Licensing	
Search and Filter Research Projects	Search function for research projects, with filters for project status (past, ongoing), research field, and keywords.
Filter by Relevance to Ocean Sustainability Challenges	Filtering option to display projects based on their relevance to ocean sustainability challenges.
Filter Research Papers by Topics	Filtering option for papers by topics related to Mission Ocean (e.g., marine conservation, sustainable fishing, blue economy).
Search & Filter Support Opportunities	Filtering support opportunities by funding type, region, or industry focus.
Filter Patents by Sector, Application, and Status	Filtering function for patents based on industry sector, application type, and status (pending, granted, expired).
Initiatives & Citizen Science	
Search and Filter Citizen Science Database	Filtering function for citizen science initiatives.
Filter Citizen Science Initiatives by EU Member State	Filtering function for citizen science initiatives country (EU Member State), policy type and measurable impact.
Filter Initiatives by Theme, Country, Policy Type, and Impact	Filtering function for blue economy initiatives based on theme, country, policy type and measurable impact.
Policies, Best Practices & Ocean Literacy	
Filter Policies by Region, Success Rate, and Policy Type	Filtering function for policy searches based on geographic scope, effectiveness, and policy category.
Filter Ocean Literacy Initiatives by Region, Audience, and Theme	Filtering function based on geographical location, target audience, and thematic focus of ocean literacy projects.
Filter Ocean Literacy Projects by 7 Principles and 10 Dimensions	Filter options for projects based on the official ocean literacy framework, focusing on the 7 Principles and 10 Dimensions.
Filtering Best Practices by Topic	Filter options for Best Practices by topic.

2.2.4 Networking & Collaboration

This category includes features that help users connect, collaborate, and share knowledge across different sectors and stakeholder groups. It enables networking between startups, investors, policymakers, researchers, and support organizations, facilitating joint proposals, funding opportunities, and commercialization efforts. Users can access dedicated collaboration tools, matchmaking features, and interactive spaces for engagement. Additionally, this category supports knowledge exchange in marine innovation, conservation, and policy, ensuring that relevant actors—such as ocean literacy networks and marine conservation groups—can easily connect, share best practices, and collaborate on impactful initiatives.

Table 5. Functionalities and Dashboard Requirements: Networking & Collaboration

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Connecting Startups, Investors & Support Organizations	
List Startups & Entrepreneurs in Marine Innovation	Interactive directory with filter and search functions for startups, including project descriptions, industry focus, and location.
Show Successful Startups in Incubation	Dedicated section showcasing case studies of successful startups, with profiles including milestones, funding rounds, and incubator details.
Matchmaking Feature for Investment Opportunities	Recommendation system suggesting relevant startups/SMEs to investors based on preferences (sector, funding stage, region).
Incubators Contact Startups via Messaging	Built-in messaging system or contact request feature enabling incubators to initiate direct conversations with startups.
Connect with Support Organizations	"Connect" button on organizational profiles allowing users to send inquiries, request meetings, or follow organizations for updates.
Collaboration on Research, Funding & Innovation	
Networking for Joint Proposals	Interactive networking tool where users can browse and join institutions seeking partners for joint funding proposals.
Networking for Joint Research and Funding	Searchable collaboration hub allowing researchers and institutions to find and connect with potential partners based on research focus, funding eligibility, and region.
Tools for Creating and Promoting Joint Initiatives and Funding Opportunities	Dedicated section for users to create, post, and promote joint initiatives with built-in announcement and sharing functionalities.
Collaboration Feature for Applied Research and Commercialization	Matching tool that connects researchers with industry partners based on shared interests in applied research, innovation, and commercialization.
Collaboration and Partnering in Knowledge Transfer	Collaboration tools for partnering in technology transfer and policy uptake, and research commercialization, with discussion threads and document sharing.
Collaboration in Knowledge Outputs and TRL	TRL (Technology Readiness Level) tracking dashboard where research teams can collaborate on outputs, provide updates, and access funding or industry connections.
Funding Opportunities and Collaboration Partners for Ocean Literacy	Search and filter feature for identifying funding sources and strategic partnerships within the ocean literacy community.
Knowledge & Policy Networking	
Connect with Relevant Projects Based on Regional Priorities	Matchmaking tool that suggests relevant projects based on regional focus, user interests, and research themes.
Engage with Policymakers and Organizations Implementing Conservation Policies	Contact and engagement feature enabling direct outreach to policymakers, with messaging or request-for-meeting options.
Interactive Forum or Consultation Feature for Regulators	Discussion forum or structured Q&A space where regulators can consult stakeholders, collect feedback, and engage in policy dialogues.
Dedicated Section for Sharing Best Practices Between Ocean Literacy Networks	Knowledge-sharing repository with categorized best practices, case studies, and discussion threads for ocean literacy networks.
Resource Section for Marine Conservation Groups	Centralized resource hub where conservation groups can share reports, tools, and success stories, with tagging and search features.
Contact Information and Activities of Ocean Literacy Networks	Searchable database of ocean literacy networks, displaying key contacts, activities, and collaboration opportunities.

Contact Details and Activities of Marine Conservation Groups	Directory of marine conservation groups with profiles detailing their mission, activities, and potential partnership opportunities.
Connect with Other Ocean Literacy Networks	Networking tool allowing users to explore, follow, and message other ocean literacy networks for potential collaboration.

2.2.5 User Experience & Interaction

This category ensures that the Dashboard is both engaging and easy to use by combining usability, accessibility, and interactive features. It includes responsive design for seamless access across devices, intuitive navigation (e.g., auto-closing filter boxes, clear explanations for filters and tabs), and features that enhance user participation, such as notifications, shareable initiative links, and alerts for funding opportunities. By providing clickable descriptions, tooltips, and structured explanations, this category helps users navigate, explore, and engage with content effectively—whether browsing initiatives, filtering information, or understanding key Dashboard elements.

Table 6. Functionalities and Dashboard Requirements: User Experience & Interaction

Functionality	Dashboard Requirements
Navigation & Usability Enhancements	
Mission Ocean Overview on the Home Screen	A brief description with a link to official information.
Responsive Design for Small Screens	Adaptive interface ensuring full functionality on devices with screens 14 inches or smaller.
Filter Boxes Automatically Close When Selecting a New One	Filters auto-collapse when a new filter is selected, preventing clutter.
Solutions Tab Explanation	Tooltip or info box clarifying whether solutions align with Mission Ocean objectives or represent project results.
Mission Ocean Objectives Filter Displays Descriptive Text	Full-text descriptions for objectives instead of numerical references.
"Explore" Tabs Provide Brief Explanations When Clicked	Inline pop-up descriptions explaining sections like "Projects" and "Stakeholders" upon selection.
Show Descriptions for Participation Levels in Citizen Science	Clickable participation levels with expandable comparisons and role explanations.
Access & Visibility	
Project Registration for Mission Dashboard Inclusion	Enable projects to register and be included in the Mission Dashboard pilot, linking them to relevant Mission objectives and thematic focus areas.
Shareable Initiative Links Without Login	Publicly accessible direct links for each initiative to facilitate easy sharing.
Access Citizen Science Database Without Login	Open access to search and filter citizen science initiatives without registration.
Display Initiative Details Without Limitations	Full initiative details available to all users, no restrictions on browsing.
Notifications & Alerts	
Set Alerts for Funding Opportunities	User-defined alert system for new funding opportunities based on research focus and location.
Notifications for New Publications	Personalized notifications for newly published research in the user's selected fields.
Notifications About Emerging Trends in Ocean Literacy	Regular updates on innovations, best practices, and policy developments in ocean literacy.

2.3 Dashboard concept

Based on WaveLinks, the future Mission Dashboard should serve as the central interface for users, consolidating key functionalities and providing an intuitive overview of relevant information. Derived from the defined dashboard requirements, the concept ensures seamless navigation, personalized content, and efficient access to critical data.

Building on the information architecture and navigation structure, the dashboard should integrate essential features such as search and filtering options, interactive data visualizations, notifications, and quick access to collaboration tools. It is designed to accommodate diverse user needs, from startups and investors to researchers, policymakers, and citizen science contributors.

To enhance usability, the dashboard should incorporate clear categorization of content, dynamic widgets displaying real-time updates, and customizable sections that allow users to tailor their experience. Key design elements include responsive layouts, accessibility considerations, and a visually engaging yet functional interface that balances data density with clarity.

This section outlines the core components that should be included in the dashboard, detailing its structure, functionalities, and interactive elements that facilitate user engagement and decision-making. The dashboard concept uses the SDU WaveLinks system as a starting point for mocking up user interfaces. An actual implementation requires deep integration with that system.

2.3.1 Information Architecture

This step defines the overall structure that the Dashboard should have, ensuring a logical flow and intuitive navigation. A well-organized architecture helps users efficiently access relevant information and functionalities, improving their overall experience. Clear categorization and a structured layout support seamless interaction with the Dashboard's content.

2.3.1.1 Main Categories

To ensure a structured and user-friendly experience, the Dashboard should be organized into key sections that align with its core functionalities. Based on the defined requirements, the following categories represent potential main sections:

1. **Research & Innovation**
 - Search & filter research projects
 - Research Papers Database
 - Technology transfer & patents
2. **Startups & Investors**
 - Discover Startups & Entrepreneurs
 - Access Contact Information
 - Matchmaking for investors, entrepreneurs & support organizations
3. **Citizen Science & Ocean Literacy**
 - Explore citizen science initiatives
 - Search & filter ocean literacy projects
 - Best practices & policy networking

4. **Policy & Regulation**
 - Track policy evolution
 - Compare legal frameworks by country
 - Analyse blue economy policies
5. **Funding**
 - Funding Opportunities Database
 - Matchmaking for Funding Partners
 - Grants & Calls Overview
6. **Solutions**
 - Solution Repository
 - Search & Filter Solutions
 - Solution Impact & Case Studies
7. **Networking & Collaboration**
 - Connect with partners for joint proposals
 - Interactive forum for policymakers
 - Knowledge transfer & impact tracking
8. **Monitoring**
 - Track Mission Progress
 - Analyse Key Performance Indicators
 - Compare Trends Over Time
9. **Personalization**
 - User profile & saved projects
 - Set alerts for funding and publications
 - Personalized recommendations

2.3.1.2 Pages & Subpages

Figure 2. Sidemap of pages & subpages

To ensure intuitive navigation and a seamless user experience, the Dashboard's structure should be organized into main pages and corresponding subpages. These pages reflect the Dashboard's core functionalities and allow users to efficiently access relevant content, tools, and networking features.

Each main page represents a key category and is further divided into subpages that provide specific functionalities, such as filtering research projects, accessing funding opportunities, or exploring matchmaking options.

The structure should be designed to enhance usability, enabling users to easily discover, interact, and collaborate within the Dashboard.

The user interface concept for the "Home" section of the Mission Ocean Dashboard (Figure 3) should provide an intuitive and structured overview. The left-hand navigation menu will allow easy access to different Dashboard sections, with "Home" highlighted to indicate the current page.

At the top, a welcome header will introduce the Dashboard, followed by a full-width "Mission Ocean and Waters Overview" card offering key insights into the Dashboard's goals. Below, an example of four distinct content blocks display featured projects & startups, the latest policy updates, trending research & funding opportunities, and My Network, ensuring users can quickly engage with relevant topics.

Figure 3. User interface concept for the "Home" section

Figure 4 illustrates the user interface concept for the "Search & Filter Research Projects" section within the Research & Innovation category, to show how it should be designed for intuitive navigation and efficient project discovery.

The left-hand menu provides structured access to sections, with the selected page highlighted for clarity. Users can search by keywords, apply filters based on categories, funding sources, or project status, and view project listings with key details.

Figure 4. User interface concept for the "Search & Filter Research Projects" section

2.3.2 Navigation

The navigation should be intuitive, allowing users to access information with minimal effort. It defines how users move through the Dashboard, interact with different sections, and engage with key features. A well-designed navigation system enhances usability and ensures an efficient user experience.

2.3.2.1 Interactive Elements

Interactive elements are essential for ensuring smooth navigation and enhancing user engagement. The Dashboard should be designed with intuitive filters, interactive buttons, and notifications that help users refine searches, interact with relevant content, and stay updated on important developments.

To facilitate easy navigation, the **Key Navigation Features** comprise:

- **Main Menu (Top Navigation):** Provides quick access to major Dashboard categories.
- **Sidebar Menu (On Category Pages):** Offers filters and subcategories for more detailed exploration.
- **Search Bar:** Enables global searches across research projects, funding, policies, and startups.
- **Filters & Sorting:** Allows users to refine searches using dropdowns, checkboxes, and auto complete.
- **Breadcrumbs:** Helps users track their location within the Dashboard for better orientation.

Beyond navigation, **Interactive Elements** also foster engagement and networking through:

- **"Connect" Buttons:** Facilitate networking with startups, investors, and experts.
- **Messaging Feature:** Enables direct communication between users.
- **Quick Actions:** One-click options to save projects, follow updates, or contact relevant stakeholders.

Additionally, **Notifications and Alerts** keep users informed about critical updates, using features such as:

- In-App Notifications: Updates on new research, funding opportunities, and policy changes.
- Email Alerts: Personalized updates based on user preferences.
- Banners & Pop-ups: Highlight critical updates and deadlines.

To ensure an intuitive and user-friendly experience, the Dashboard should follow best practices in navigation design, including clear menu labels, mobile responsiveness, and visual cues such as icons and highlights. Quick-action functionalities, like one-click saving of projects or direct connection options, further enhance usability, making it easier for users to interact with the Dashboard efficiently.

These interactive elements will ensure a smooth user experience, making it easy to discover, explore, and engage with relevant content.

2.3.2.2 Searching the Semantic Network

To facilitate effective knowledge management within the Mission Ocean ecosystem (MOE), WP4 of P4B developed a semantic network supported by an ontology developed in Task 4.1. This network provides the foundation for linking Mission-related activities, and knowledge domains. Together with the Mission Ecosystem Database (DB), the semantic network enables a structured and interoperable exchange of expertise, best practices, and solutions. The MOE DB and ontology are described in greater detail in [D4.1](#) and [D4.3](#).

The MOE spans diverse domains—including research, legal frameworks, citizen engagement, and business models—each with its own ontologies and vocabularies. Without alignment, these domains remain isolated knowledge "islands." Ontology alignment ensures that different sets of information, often categorized using distinct terminologies, can interoperate seamlessly. It functions as a translation layer, mapping different terms to their equivalent meanings, much like recognizing that "cars" and "automobiles" refer to the same concept.

A core functionality of the Dashboard will be to allow users to search through and interact with the semantic network. To achieve this, an intuitive search interface is required. The choice of visualization methods — whether graph-based navigation, interactive filtering, or hierarchical structures — must consider the complexity of the network, the target audience, and the purpose of the search.

For our dashboard, we have identified two visualization methods as the most effective: a Force-Directed Graph and a list view.

The Force-Directed Graph provides an interactive and dynamic visualization, ideal for exploratory data analysis. It closely aligns with the Neo4j browser used in this project for navigating the Mission Ocean ecosystem (MOE), making it a natural choice for users needing a more in-depth and relational view of the data.

The list view offers a straightforward, structured representation of nodes and their relationships, making it particularly useful for non-experts, such as citizens, who need a simple and easily understandable way to access information.

Via an 'Explore' button, for example, from the project search view, users can access the respective visualization of the network to explore it (Figure 5).

Home

Search

Research & Innovation

Search Research Projects

Research Papers Database

Technology Transfer

Startups & Investors

Citizen Science & Ocean

Literacy

Policy & Regulation

Funding

Solutions

Networking & Collaboration

Monitoring

Personalization

Search research projects...

Marine Data AI

Developing AI models for oceanographic data analysis.

View Project

Explore

Blue Carbon Initiative

Studying carbon sequestration in marine ecosystems.

View Project

Explore

Sustainable Fisheries Research

Assessing fish stock sustainability and best practices.

View Project

Explore

Figure 5. User interface concept for the " Search & Filter Research Projects " section including "Explore"-Button

After clicking "Explore," the selected project is pinned at the top, providing a clear reference point while exploring the network. Below, the outlined exploration area allows users to navigate the network (Figure 6). In the top right corner of this section, a small "X" button enables users to close the view and return to the project list. Next to it, a list icon allows seamless switching between the list view and the force-directed graph.

Within the exploration area, users will be able to interact with the force-directed graph to explore related projects, relevant research papers, key stakeholders, funding opportunities, policy connections, and other linked initiatives. This dynamic approach enables an intuitive and visually engaging way to uncover synergies and deepen understanding of interconnected topics.

Figure 6. User interface concept for Searching the Semantic Network – Graph

In the list view, the selected project remains pinned at the top as the primary "search subject". Below, entities connected to the project through specific properties are displayed as "search suggestions" (Figure 7). These entities represent different types of relationships within the network.

These entities may include:

- Type – Categorization, such as Lighthouse area/basin or thematic focus (e.g., ecology, sensors)
- Place – The geographical location related to the project (e.g., North Sea).
- Time-span – The project's duration (e.g., 2022–2025).
- Actor – Involved organizations or individuals (e.g., Fraunhofer).
- Activity – Actions related to the project, such as Mission objectives.
- Creation – Related publications or outputs.

When clicking on a suggested entity, a list of matching results should appear (Figure 8). These results may include related research projects (since this view is part of the "Search Research Projects" section) or additional suggestions leading to further connections. For example, selecting a publication could reveal its author, and clicking on the author would then display projects to which they have contributed.

Each selection—whether a project or an entity—gets pinned underneath the original project, forming a hierarchical exploration path. This allows users to track their journey through the network, seeing each step they took. At any point, users can re-enter from a previously selected node and explore a different path, dynamically navigating the research ecosystem while uncovering new relevant connections.

- Home
- Search
 - Research & Innovation
 - [Search Research Projects](#)
 - Research Papers Database
 - Technology Transfer
 - Startups & Investors
 - Citizen Science & Ocean Literacy
 - Policy & Regulation
 - Funding
 - Solutions
- Networking & Collaboration
- Monitoring
- Personalization

Q
▽

Marine Data AI
Developing AI models for oceanographic data analysis.

☰ ×

North Sea Basin

Sensor Technology

Marine Biodiversity Monitoring

Objective 3: Protect and restore marine ecosystems and biodiversity

Figure 7. User interface concept for Searching the Semantic Network – List: Search Suggestions

- Home
- Search
 - Research & Innovation
 - [Search Research Projects](#)
 - Research Papers Database
 - Technology Transfer
 - Startups & Investors
 - Citizen Science & Ocean Literacy
 - Policy & Regulation
 - Funding
 - Solutions
- Networking & Collaboration
- Monitoring
- Personalization

Q
▽

Marine Data AI
Developing AI models for oceanographic data analysis.

☰ ×

Sensor Technology

Ocean Sensor Network
Developing a real-time ocean monitoring system. View Project

Smart Buoys Initiative
Deploying smart buoys to track water quality. View Project

Figure 8. User interface concept for Searching the Semantic Network – List: Related Projects

2.3.3 Visual Design

The visual design of the Dashboard should follow the corporate design of P4B, ensuring a consistent and recognizable appearance. The selected colours and fonts align with the established branding, prioritizing clarity, accessibility, and a professional yet modern aesthetic. The colour palette primarily should consist of shades of blue and white, reinforcing the aquatic focus, with contrasting accent colours for interactive elements such as buttons and icons. The typography is clean and legible, using a sans-serif font to maintain a contemporary look.

Buttons, Cards, Lists, and Tables

The user interface (UI) components (see Figure 5 for buttons, cards and lists) should be designed for clarity and usability:

- Buttons: Rounded corners, subtle shadows, and clear labels to indicate actions. Primary actions use a distinct colour, while secondary buttons have an outlined or muted design.
- Cards: Used for project previews and key content sections, featuring a minimalistic style with a clear title, concise description, and action buttons (e.g., “View Project,” “Explore”).
- Lists: Structured for easy scanning, with search suggestions and related entities visually separated. Indentation is used to show hierarchy when needed.
- Tables: Clean grid layout, alternating row colours for readability, and minimal borders to avoid visual clutter.

Icons & Symbols for Navigation

Icons should enhance usability and intuitive navigation, representing key functions like search, filtering, exploring networks, and switching views. The design prioritizes universally recognized symbols (see Figure 6 & Figure 7):

- Magnifying glass for search
- Filter icon for refining results
- Graph/network symbol for switching to the force-directed graph view
- List icon for switching to the list view
- Close (X) icon for returning to the previous screen

Dark Mode / Light Mode

A light mode design should be the standard, ensuring readability and consistency with the overall Dashboard aesthetic. A dark mode option is not necessary at this stage.

This visual approach will ensure a cohesive, user-friendly, and professional interface that aligns with the P4B corporate identity while enhancing usability for diverse user groups.

3 Tracking of Mission progress

Tracking the progress of Mission Ocean and Waters requires a structured approach to monitoring key developments, assessing achievements, and identifying areas where further efforts are needed. To achieve this, a systematic framework is needed that enables the visualization, analysis, and interpretation of Mission-related activities and outcomes.

This section presents the concept for tracking Mission progress by integrating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) into the Mission dashboard. The approach builds on the semantic network structure, linking projects, stakeholders, and outcomes to relevant Mission objectives (already carried out in WaveLinks). By doing so, the dashboard will serve as a dynamic tool for monitoring how different initiatives contribute to the Mission's overall goals.

An initial assessment has been conducted to explore the feasibility of this approach, focusing on capturing and structuring available data points related to Mission activities. This first step provides a foundation for integrating structured tracking methodologies, allowing for better insights into progress assessment and future refinements. This section outlines the selected KPIs, visualization strategies, and initial insights gained from this assessment. It also highlights key challenges and recommendations for improving the tracking methodology to ensure that Mission progress can be effectively monitored and communicated.

3.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Mission Progress

Tracking Mission progress requires well-defined KPIs to measure achievements and assess impact. These indicators help monitor the effectiveness of implemented actions and guide future efforts. This section outlines key indicators and methods for evaluating progress, ensuring a structured approach to measuring success.

3.1.1 Definition and Selection of KPIs

To effectively assess the progress of the Mission, it is essential to define and select key performance indicators (KPIs) that provide measurable insights into its implementation and impact. The chosen KPIs should reflect the Mission's core objectives, capturing scientific advancements, policy developments, stakeholder engagement, and environmental and societal outcomes. This section outlines the relevant KPIs that serve as benchmarks for evaluating Mission progress.

We selected the KPIs (Table 7) based on available open data sources for projects, such as CORDIS, UN Ocean Decade, BlueBio Cofund, *etc.* which are also used by the WaveLinks database and based on potential automation. Similarly, to the [Knowledge Transfer Online Showcasing Module \(D4.5\)](#), semantic alignment with the MOE ontology enables automatic evaluation of many of the proposed KPIs, which would otherwise be infeasible or require much more manual intervention to track. For some of the KPIs a link to publication and funding databases beyond the current connections is necessary.

The following list is colour-coded as follows:

- Already implemented in WaveLinks
- Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
- Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
- Relevant, but poor data availability
- Relevant, but hard to track programmatically

Table 7. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Mission Progress: Suggestions, Status and/or Feasibility

KPI	Status and/or Feasibility
Implementation and Activities	
Number of research projects implemented within the Mission	■ Already implemented in WaveLinks
Number of milestones achieved within projects. This is highly recommended, but data is currently not available.	■ Relevant, but poor data availability
Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of solutions developed under the Mission.	■ Already implemented in WaveLinks
Number of developed and deployed innovative technologies.	■ Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Number of funded projects and total amount of allocated grants/funding	■ Already implemented in WaveLinks
Share of solutions/knowledge outputs successfully transferred to practice	■ Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Transfer path: Number of technologies/solutions progressing from research to application	■ Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Scientific Advancements & Publications	
Number of scientific publications related to the Mission	■ Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Number of citations of Mission-related publications	■ Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Number of publications per research field (e.g., Marine Biology, Climate Change)	■ Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Number of authors and organizations (Authors/Organizations) contributing to Mission research	■ Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Interdisciplinarity: Number of publications covering multiple research fields	■ Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.

KPI	Status and/or Feasibility
Policy and Regulatory Developments	
Number of policy measures influenced by Mission-related research	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Number of relevant legislative documents linked to Mission-related topics	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Number of amendments or new regulations recorded in the database	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Integration of Mission results into national/international policy frameworks	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Stakeholder Engagement & Networking	
Number of engaged stakeholders (<i>e.g.</i> , research institutions, companies, NGOs)	Already implemented in WaveLinks
Number of stakeholder workshops or networking events conducted	Relevant, but poor data availability
Number of Citizen Initiatives (see WP3)	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Cross-sector collaborations: Number of partnerships across different sectors	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Number of participating Stakeholders per countries and regions	Already implemented in WaveLinks
Number of participating countries and regions actively conducting Mission projects	Already implemented in WaveLinks
Environmental and Societal Impact	
Improvements in environmental indicators (<i>e.g.</i> , water quality, biodiversity, CO ₂ sequestration)	Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Reduction in environmental pressures (<i>e.g.</i> , plastic pollution, nutrient discharge)	Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Number of legislative measures addressing environmental improvements	Relevant, but hard to track programmatically
Number of projects directly aligned with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), currently not addressed, but strongly recommended	Relevant, but poor data availability
Identification of new business opportunities: Number of innovations with economic potential	Feasible by including the MOE ontology and D4.5
Number of established best practices for scaling and replication	Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.
Number of regions monitored for environmental changes documented by Mission projects	Feasible using available data in WaveLinks or other open data sources.

The selected KPIs provide a structured approach to monitoring the Mission’s progress, covering scientific, policy, stakeholder, and environmental dimensions. These indicators serve as a foundation for evaluating impact, guiding strategic decisions, and ensuring that the Mission’s objectives translate into tangible outcomes.

3.1.2 Methods for Measuring Progress

Assessing progress requires a combination of baseline comparisons, time-series analyses, and qualitative or quantitative methods. These approaches help track developments over time, identify trends, and measure the impact of Mission-related activities. While current evaluations rely on available data, future improvements—such as more systematic data collection and long-term tracking—will enhance the depth and accuracy of assessments.

Baseline Comparisons

Baseline data serve as a reference point for measuring change over time. By comparing current values to an initial state, progress can be quantified. In cases where baseline data are unavailable, proxy indicators or historical records may be used to establish a starting point.

Time-Series Analyses

Longitudinal data collection enables the identification of trends and patterns. Tracking key indicators over time helps determine whether progress is accelerating, stagnating, or declining. Visualization tools, such as dashboards and graphs, facilitate the interpretation of these trends.

Qualitative vs. Quantitative Approaches

Both qualitative and quantitative methods contribute to a comprehensive assessment.

- Quantitative methods involve measurable data, such as the number of projects, funding allocated, or publications produced. These provide objective metrics for comparison.
- Qualitative methods capture insights that may not be reflected in numerical data, such as stakeholder perceptions, policy impacts, or barriers to implementation. Surveys, interviews, and case studies can supplement quantitative findings.

As data availability improves, refinements such as real-time tracking, advanced analytics, and integrated data sources will enhance the accuracy and depth of progress assessments. Challenges and recommendations regarding future tracking of KPIs are given below in 3.3.

3.2 Visualization in the Dashboard

Tracking progress requires clear and intuitive visual representations of key performance indicators (KPIs). To ensure accessibility and usability, KPIs should be integrated into the "Monitoring" section of the dashboard, where data is updated regularly. Users should be able to filter indicators by time periods, regions, and thematic focus areas, enabling targeted insights. The dashboard should employ various visualization methods, including charts, maps, and trend graphs, to facilitate quick assessments and comparative analysis.

Different types of KPIs require tailored visualization methods:

- Numerical Indicators (*e.g.*, number of funded projects, research outputs, participating organizations)
→ Simple Counters & Trend Graphs
- Comparative Metrics (*e.g.*, progress vs. target, distribution across categories)
→ Bar Charts & Pie Charts
- Temporal Trends (*e.g.*, evolution of funding, number of projects over time)
→ Line Graphs & Time-Series Charts
- Geospatial Data (*e.g.*, project locations, country participation)
→ Interactive Maps

The dashboard should provide a structured visualization of key performance indicators (KPIs) to track the progress and impact of Mission Ocean and Waters activities. The dashboard features the Mission Progress Overview as well as five KPI categories mentioned in chapter 3.1.1, each represented by an interactive tile that can dynamically adjust in size.

Figure 9. User interface concept for the "Monitoring" section

This KPI-based structure allows stakeholders to quickly assess progress, identify gaps, and explore key developments in Mission Ocean and Waters' efforts toward sustainability and innovation, while also enabling personalization of the dashboard to meet individual needs.

An example of how a KPI tile may look like is illustrated in Figure 10, showcasing the category "Stakeholder Engagement & Networking." This tile visually represents key metrics and insights related to collaboration efforts, partnerships, and stakeholder involvement in Mission Ocean and Waters activities, providing users with an intuitive understanding of performance in this area.

Stakeholder Engagement & Networking

Figure 10. User interface concept for the “Monitoring” section – Stakeholder Engagement & Networking

3.3 Challenges and Recommendations for Future Tracking

Tracking the progress of the Mission presents several technical and methodological challenges that need to be addressed for effective monitoring and evaluation. These challenges relate to data availability, interoperability, and the integration of different tracking approaches. Additionally, improving the scalability and usability of the tracking framework is key to ensuring its long-term impact across multiple European marine regions.

3.3.1 Technical and Methodological Challenges

1. Data Availability and Integration

- A key challenge in tracking Mission progress is ensuring comprehensive data availability. Many indicators rely on fragmented or project-specific datasets, requiring standardization and aggregation across multiple sources.
- Integrating diverse data types (*e.g.*, numerical KPIs, qualitative assessments, geospatial data) into a cohesive framework remains a complex task.
- Ensuring interoperability between different data providers, research institutions, and policy frameworks is necessary for an effective cross-sector monitoring approach.

2. Semantic Network and KPI Alignment

- While numerical indicators provide measurable insights, they often lack contextual depth. Integrating the semantic network structure (linking projects, stakeholders, and thematic areas) with KPI tracking can enhance understanding by connecting metrics to underlying Mission activities and relationships.
- Users should be able to explore interconnections between different KPIs and relevant entities (*e.g.*, how a research project contributes to policy changes or technological advancements).

3.3.2 Recommendations for Future Implementation

1. Strengthening the Semantic-KPI Link

- As the KPI list above indicates, linking KPIs to entities within the semantic network enables two key types of features: First, numerical evaluation of previously intractable indicators becomes possible. Second, users can explore progress beyond numerical values, tracing the impact of projects through research outputs, stakeholder contributions, and policy adoption.
- This approach fosters knowledge transfer, demonstrating how research initiatives translate into practical applications and policy influence.

2. Enhancing Data Quality, Adding Data Sources and Standardization

- Establishing consistent data collection protocols across Mission-related projects can improve tracking accuracy and comparability.
- Developing automated data aggregation methods (*e.g.*, API connections with funding agencies, research databases) will facilitate real-time updates.
- Integrate project reviews and other internal information for the tracking of ongoing projects. The current data sources focus on finished projects and their outcome only.

3. Scaling the Approach Across European Marine Regions

- The current framework already incorporates multiple European marine regions and should continue to be flexible and adaptable to different geographical and thematic contexts.
- Standardizing KPI definitions and integrating them with international frameworks (*e.g.*, UN Sustainable Development Goals, EU Green Deal targets) can ensure wide applicability.
- A modular approach to scaling the dashboard infrastructure can support additional datasets, user needs, and future expansions.

By addressing these challenges and implementing the recommended improvements, the Mission dashboard can evolve into a powerful tool for tracking progress, facilitating decision-making, and supporting evidence-based policy actions at both regional and international levels.

4 Conclusion

The future development of the Mission Dashboard through WaveLinks⁵ and the structured approach to tracking Mission progress are key steps in supporting the implementation of the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

This report provides recommendations on the conceptual foundation, functionalities, and user-centred design of the Mission Dashboard, ensuring it serves as an accessible and effective tool for stakeholders. By applying *Requirements Engineering (RE)* principles, the proposed dashboard will integrate user needs, structured user stories, and acceptance criteria, resulting in an improved WaveLinks system that enhances situational awareness, decision-making, and collaboration across different marine regions.

At the same time, tracking Mission progress relies on well-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that measure achievements, assess impact, and provide insights into the effectiveness of implemented actions. Our proposed KPIs are both feasible to implement with available data and capture the Mission progress across multiple facets. The integration of these KPIs into the dashboard will ensure continuous monitoring, enabling stakeholders to evaluate trends, identify gaps, and refine strategies from their respective perspective. Our study reveals key challenges related to data availability, interoperability, and visualization. Addressing these challenges through improved data collection methods and expanded tracking capabilities will further strengthen the monitoring framework. The MOE plays a critical role in providing structured access to the complicated connections between projects, outcomes and stakeholders, so that KPIs can be evaluated automatically.

Looking ahead, WaveLinks could continue evolving into the Mission Dashboard, providing an essential tool for the Mission, facilitating data-driven decision-making and fostering transparency. Partially, the proposed and requested features have already been implemented in SDU's WaveLinks through the project. Future steps will focus on refining the KPI framework, enhancing data integration, and improving visualization techniques to provide more actionable insights.

The ongoing development and adaptation of WaveLinks lay the foundation for a lasting digital infrastructure that extends beyond the lifetime of the project. By continuously improving usability and relevance, the dashboard can serve as a long-term resource for tracking progress, supporting evidence-based policy, and enabling collaboration across European marine regions. In this way, the Mission Dashboard can become a lasting legacy, ensuring that insights, data, and impact remain accessible and actionable well into the future.

⁵ WaveLinks wavelinks.eu